

**STUDENT RESPONSE TO THE INTEGRATION OF ONLINE EDUCATION IN HIGH
SCHOOL PHYSICS CLASSROOMS: A CASE STUDY**

SAMANTHA CLARK

A THESIS IN
THE DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

PRESENTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE

OF

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE WITH HONOURS (PHYSICS)

AT

CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY

MONTREAL, QC, CANADA

MAY 2021

ABSTRACT

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, high school classrooms in the province of Quebec had to switch to a half-in-person and half-online attendance, reducing in-person class sizes to follow the physical distancing requirements. With very few studies examining this education model, this study aims to investigate the teacher and student response, as well as observe its impact on student engagement within the high school physics classroom. Ten students in the same Grade 11 physics classroom participated in this case study. Two surveys, completed at the beginning and end of the 2020 fall semester, respectively, were used to evaluate the progression of the student's physics interest, study habits, preferred learning methods and engagement in online and in-person settings over the course of the semester. Additionally, the instructor and five students volunteered to be interviewed. These interviews provided a deeper understanding of the survey data, as well as insight on the student's emotional response to their new classroom setting. Results indicated that while the majority of the participants preferred to attend classes in-person, the half/half model was highly ranked, as a significant portion of the students mentioned its advantages. Technical difficulties, isolation and the increased workload were the main reasons for the lower motivation to attend school online. However, most students enjoyed the increased efficiency, schedule flexibility, comfort, and the ability to simultaneously cooperate with peers during teacher-led lectures when attending classes online. The students' motivation to take the course, and their overall satisfaction and criticism of the course was found to be independent of the classroom setting and of the students' main learning type – be it visual, auditory or kinetic.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I first want to thank my supervisor, Dr. Calvin Kalman for accepting to supervise me despite my lack of experience in physics education research. Thank you for helping me shape my research question so that it was achievable and meaningful despite the limitations we had to face. I'm grateful for your continuous feedback and support throughout this past year, but most importantly, thank you for showing me what it means to be a great teacher and inspiring me to pursue physics education as a career.

I would also like to thank Mme Marie-Claude Dupuis for letting me join your classes and taking the extra time to show me as much as you could even when your schedule was already full. Your passion and dedication to the students showed me that teaching is so much more than just presenting course material to students. You taught me that encouragement and support can make any student succeed no matter their experience or skill level.

Thank you as well to all the physics students at Westwood High School, particularly to those who gave their time and shared their experiences with me during the research process. I wish you all success in your exams, and in all your future endeavors.

Thank you to Franco La Braca, Joseph El-Helou, Mandana Sobhanzadeh, and Mark Lattery for your constructive feedback and insight during our meetings. Your advice was instrumental in the making of this study.

Thank you to my friends and family who encouraged me to pursue this topic and supported me throughout the whole process. Your love and care were key to helping me keep on track and staying motivated.

Finally, a special thank you to Kaitlin for your many read throughs, edits, and daily reminders to keep working hard. I could not have done this without you.

Samantha Clark

April 2021

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	1
Defining Online Learning.....	2
Totally Online Learning	2
Time Requirements to Develop Online Courses.....	4
Mixed Mode Online Learning	5
Student Engagement.....	6
Purpose of this Study.....	7
METHODS	8
Participants	8
Classroom Environment.....	9
Procedure	9
Data Trustworthiness	11
Survey Data Analysis.....	11
Interview Data Analysis.....	12
Observational Data.....	14
RESULTS	15
Social interactions.....	15
Administrative / Teacher Issues	18
Academic & Technical Skills	20
Learner Motivation & Satisfaction.....	21
Time & Support for Studies	24
Technology.....	26
Learning Environment	27
Physics Learning Methods & Understanding.....	29
DISCUSSION	33
CONCLUSION	38
REFERENCES	39
<i>Appendix A: Student Information and Consent Form</i>	<i>44</i>
<i>Appendix B: Parental Information and Consent Form</i>	<i>47</i>
<i>Appendix C: Student Assent Form</i>	<i>50</i>
<i>Appendix D: Instructor Information and Consent Form</i>	<i>53</i>

<i>Appendix E: First Survey – October 2020</i>	55
<i>Appendix F: Second Survey – December 2020</i>	64
<i>Appendix G: Student Interview Guide</i>	71
<i>Appendix H: Teacher Interview Guide</i>	73

Table of Figures

Figure 1	2
Figure 2	4
Figure 3	13
Figure 4	17
Figure 5	17
Figure 6	20
Figure 7	21
Figure 8	22
Figure 9	22
Figure 10	23
Figure 11	24
Figure 12	25
Figure 13	27
Figure 14	28
Figure 15	29
Figure 16	30
Figure 17	31

INTRODUCTION

On March 11th, 2020, the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 as a pandemic and called for countries “to take urgent and aggressive action,” (World Health Organization, 2020). As the virus spread rapidly across Canadian cities, the government quickly implemented measures to slow down its progression. Province-wide lockdowns caused universities and schools to shut down (Bronca, 2020), resulting in many schools looking to switch classes to an online format. In Quebec, the Premier mentioned that “while CEGEPs and university will be able to resume classes online by March 30, it is ‘unlikely’ that children will be back by that date,” (Hinkson & Marchand, 2020).

On March 12th, 2020, Westwood Senior High School posted on their Facebook page that the school board and administration had made the decision to close the school from March 13th until further notice and that “students are encouraged to check Classroom and keep up with any work they have at home,” (Westwood Senior High School, 2020). On March 16th, the school replied to a comment on their Facebook page inquiring about the possibility of online classes as follows:

At present, our directives from the Government are not to provide work. You’ll notice that private schools do not have to follow this directive. We anticipate an update from the Government and the Board in the near future if the situation is likely to go on into April. We will update as soon as we know anything.

On April 16th, the public high school launched its own website dedicated to providing work for its students (Westwood Senior High School, 2020). On April 27th, the Quebec’s Ministry of Education announced that distance learning would continue “for all secondary school students and adult learners until the end of the school year,” (Québec Ministère de l’Éducation, 2020). During her interview, the physics teacher explained that she held lectures for any interested student over Zoom, preparing them for CEGEP as best she could from the resources she had at home, for the remainder of the academic year.

For the 2020-2021 academic year, the Minister of Education, sent out a letter detailing the government’s return-to-school protocol, stating that Secondary IV and V students would follow “an alternating schedule, where students are in class every second day and complete distance learning and assignments at home,” (Roberge, 2020, p.2). Following this guideline, each class at

Westwood Senior High School was divided in two sections, A or B, with each containing half of its usual number of students. Over its repeating nine-day schedule, each section would alternate between online and in-person attendance, resulting in online attendance every second day (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Sample Westwood High School Weekly Schedule

Date	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
	September 14	September 15	September 16	September 17	September 18
Day	3A	3B	4A	4B	5A

Note: Academic week based on 2020-2021 Lester B. Pearson School Board calendar

Defining Online Learning

As outlined by Linda Harasim’s (2000) article, there are three main categories of online education:

- *Adjunct mode* which uses networking to enhance traditional face-to-face or distance education.
- *Mixed mode* which employs networking as significant portion of a traditional classroom or distance course.
- *Totally online mode* which relies on networking as the primary teaching medium for an entire course or program. (p. 46)

Using these categories, the mode of education found in Quebec public high schools since the start of the COVID lockdown transitioned from being totally online to mixed. While the data for this study was acquired between September 2020 and December 2020 as the participants learned in mixed online education, many of them made comparisons with their experience of learning totally online during the end of the previous academic year.

Totally Online Learning

As its name entails, a totally online course has “most or all of its content online, and typically has no face-to-face meetings,” (Picciano, 2012, p.128). While online learning was used in Quebec during the pandemic lockdown to allow students to finish their 2019-2020 academic

year remotely, there are many other reasons why online education is implemented internationally. Online education not only makes distance learning possible, but it also reduces student and teacher travel time and costs (Harasim 2000). According to Haughey (2005), there are a number of reasons associated with the growth of online learning in Canadian K-12 schools. “Students traditionally chose distance education because of a lack of required courses, or their need for greater flexibility to allow them to compete in elite sports or arts programs, to travel with their families, or to sustain their schooling despite chronic illness or incarceration,” (Haughey, 2005). At the university level, many studies proved there were no significant differences in learning outcome between online learning and on-campus classes (Van Schaik, et al., 2003, Chen & Zimitat, 2004, and Ladyshevsky, 2004). Moreover, online education is said to facilitate collaborative learning and mutual support among students (Harasim et al., 1996). In his study, Baskin (2001) reported that the online environment improved the process of collaborative small group learning, since it was adapted from face-to-face classroom practice. However, along with other researchers (Herrington & Oliver, 2000; Paloff & Pratt, 2001), Baskin (2001) emphasized the importance of good pedagogical design for achieving this effectiveness.

A 2005 study conducted by Muilenburg & Berge, categorized student perceived barriers to online learning as follows:

- (1) *Time/interruptions* is a grouping that has to do with the perceived barriers to students’ spending time in learning online and the interruptions that may disrupt a student’s learning.
- (2) *Infrastructure/support services*. This grouping, from the students’ perspective, has to do with issues that the instructor or organization could control.
- (3) *Motivation*. This grouping has to do with the psychological processes that cause students to persist in meeting their learning goals.
- (4) *Prerequisite skills*. This grouping consists of areas that most students believe they need to have mastered to a certain degree before entering the online classroom.
- (5) *Technical*. This grouping refers to students being comfortable with the online system and the software/hardware that is being used in online learning.
- (6) *Social*. This grouping refers to the learning environment that is created for learning online which should be friendly and social, and one in which learning is promoted. This suggests promoting human relationships, developing group cohesiveness, maintaining the

group as a unit, and in other ways helping participants to work together for a mutual cause.
(p.32)

This study ranked the barrier factors from most severe to least severe (see Figure 2). These factors were used as organizational categories used to structure the survey questions used in this study, and the substantive categories derived from the participants’ interview responses.

Figure 2

Priority of Student Barriers to Online Learning

Barrier factors (<i>n</i> = 1,056)	Means	SD
Social interactions	2.36	1.07
Administrative/instructor issues	2.05	0.80
Time and support for studies	1.91	0.79
Learner motivation	1.91	0.93
Technical problems	1.70	0.73
Cost and access to the Internet	1.60	0.73
Technical skills	1.30	0.50
Academic skills	1.22	0.50

Note: Table taken directly from Muilenburg & Berge (2005, p.38).

Time Requirements to Develop Online Courses

In 2013, Lee A. Freeman published a paper entitled “Instructor Time Requirements to Develop and Teach Online Courses” outlining the response of 68 university instructors. His results showed that “when teaching a course for the first time, Content Development (85%) is clearly more time consuming for online courses than face-to-face courses. The same can be said for Pre-Semester Setup (82%) and Instructor-Student Interaction (75%), while Grading & Assessment (54%) and Overall Involvement in the Class (56%) were less so,” (Freeman, 2013). Even comparing the second and third time teaching a course in both modes showed that online courses were still more time-consuming than face-to-face courses. With 87% of the respondent requiring between 8 to 16 weeks to complete their online course development (Freeman, 2013), it seems unlikely that Quebec high school teachers managed to do the same in less than four weeks in order to finish the 2019-2020 academic year properly. Moreover, according to the interviewed teacher, Westwood High School staff were told that they would be teaching both

online and in-person simultaneously at the beginning of August 2020, leaving them less than a month to prepare their courses before the first day of classes on August 30th, 2020. Before this announcement, teachers had been preparing for a fully online class delivery. Knowing this, it seems unlikely that the teaching staff had enough time to fully develop a simultaneous blended education course days before having to teach.

Mixed Mode Online Learning

Also known as “hybrid” or “blended” learning, mixed online education has a wide range of definitions. For the purpose of this study, blended learning will be used to describe the educational mode that was used in the participants’ classes for the 2020-2021 academic year. This mode is comprised of classes where the instruction is done simultaneously online, and face-to-face, with half the students attending either remotely or in-person.

A study done by Lightner & Lightner-Laws (2013) examined the success of a graduate Management Science and Statistics course which employed simultaneous blended education. As the study explained:

The blended model proposed in this research allows students to take a quantitative graduate course traditionally, via ITV or online. Students are able to enroll in a single course and rotate between delivery modes each week at their convenience. Temporarily deployed military, absent, and online students are able to stay connected to a traditional classroom environment as well. This model provides students with the flexibility of an online environment, while maintaining the guidance and comfort of traditional instructor support. Results suggest that our model reduces (and nearly eliminates) student achievement performance gaps. (p. 236)

Other articles also mentioned having success with synchronous hybrid education in doctoral seminars (Roseth et al., 2013), “sychromodal classes for the Educational Psychology and Educational Technology (EPET) Ph.D. program,” (Bell et al., 2014) and other university level courses (Alghamdi et al., 2020, & White et al., 2010). However, there was very little literature on synchronous blended education at the secondary (K-12) level, except for a few opinion articles on websites such as EducationWeek.org. While no rigorous study was done, experienced teachers discussed “strategies for teaching students online and face to face at the same time,” (Ferlazzo, 2021). In this article, Ferlazzo (2021) recommended actively seeking the participation of online

students, having in-person and remote students interact with each other “via breakout rooms or on apps like Jamboard and Kahoot”, creating routines, setting learning expectations and giving “remote learners a variety of ways to demonstrate their engagement”. The author also recommended that teachers “find ways to celebrate their students” and “find opportunities for experiences like virtual field trips”. The article really emphasised the importance of social interactions between students and the teacher, prioritizing classroom discussions and project-based learning methods to promote student engagement.

Student Engagement

As defined by Newman (1989), “engagement is more than motivation or the general desire to succeed in school. It involves participation, connection, attachment, and integration in particular settings and tasks” (p.34). While this definition was written over thirty years ago, it still rings true; barriers to student engagement relate to isolation, separation, detachment and fragmentation. As Calvin Kalman (2018) mentions in the first chapter of his book, no matter if the material delivery is perfect, student information retention needs to be from active learning rather than passive information gathering. As he mentions in further chapters, many students lack the ability to apply principles from one program to another. There is faster intellectual development in inquiry-based courses rather than teacher-centered ones since in the former students are forced to examine their views and develop them. Kalman suggests many exercises to promote student-centered learning such as collaborative group exercises (p.33) and reflective writing (p.47) The latter was studied in a high school physics course by El-Helou & Kalman (2018) and was found to be “a low-impact, high-return tool,” (p.88). Beyond student-centered learning, there are many other factors that affect engagement. As Newman (1989) writes: “studies of schooling and research from psychology and sociology suggest the importance of five factors: students’ need for competence, extrinsic rewards, intrinsic interest, social support and sense of ownership,” (p.34). These categories, combined with the student perceived online barriers determined by Muilenburg & Berge (2005), were modified to better fit this study and then used as organizational categories to structure survey and interview questions, as well as a sorting tool during the data analysis. As such, the data collected in this study was sorted in eight separate sections, reflecting the following organizational categories: (1) social interactions, (2) administrative/instructor issues, (3)

academic/technical skills, (4) learner motivation & satisfaction, (5) time and support for studies, (6) technology, (7) learning environment, and (8) physics learning requirements.

Purpose of this Study

The purpose of this study was to fill in the gaps in literature, by identifying factors perceived by high school students that facilitate or hinder their motivation and engagement in physics classrooms doing simultaneous hybrid online learning. In order to provide an in-depth perspective on student experience, this study adopted a case-study approach, focusing on high-achieving students taught by the same physics instructor. The physics class was taught simultaneously with half the students present in class and the other half participating remotely via Zoom. Two surveys and in-depth interviews were used to examine the student perspective and were supported by in-class observations. Investigation focused on the overall experience of students between September 2020 and December 2020, on the student's motivation, as well as factors perceived by the students to be engaging or disengaging relative to their overall education experience and class experience online versus in-person. Based on literature, social interactions, administrative/instructor issues, academic & technical skills, intrinsic learner motivation & perceived satisfaction, time and support for studies, technology, learning environment, and physics learning requirements, were all considered as important factors of student engagement within simultaneous blended physics education. Additionally, the teacher's point of view and experiences were added to each section to better contextualize the student data.

METHODS

Participants

Ten Grade 11 students enrolled in *Physics 534* at Westwood High School in Hudson, Québec, participated in this study. *Physics 534*, the only physics course offered at the high school, covers “kinematics, dynamics, transformation of mechanical energy, and geometric optics,” (Québec Ministère de l'Éducation, 2021, p.21). All students participating in this study were also taking chemistry, advanced math, French, English, physical education, humanities, and either art, music, or drama concurrently. In a nine-day schedule, students attended Physics in four, 75-minute long lectures, for a total of 5 hours. There were eight females and two male participants. The five students participating in the interview process were all girls. Eight students described themselves as being high-achieving students with overall grades above 85%, and the other two students described themselves as having overall grades between 84% and 70%. When asked to describe their preferred learning style between auditory, visual, and kinetic, three students chose auditory, three students chose visual, and four students chose kinetic.

After obtaining permission from school administrators, I was allowed to attend all classes taught by the physics teacher in order to observe and occasionally help out when needed (i.e., setting up lab stations, handing out notes/assignments, etc.). Participants were recruited in person over the course of two weeks due to the half/half schedule, as I introduced myself and the study to whichever section was present in class. This was done while the teacher organized the students attending the class remotely through Zoom and did not interfere with lecturing time. After a complete overview detailing what participation would entail and the objectives of the study, an information package containing both the student and parental Information and Consent forms (see Appendix A, and Appendix B), as well as the Student Assent form (see Appendix C) were distributed to each student, as per the university's research ethics requirements. Of the students who showed interest, eleven students returned their consent forms fully completed and properly signed. One participant subsequently withdrew from the study after failing to complete the first survey in time, and never responding to further emails.

The instructor also participated in this study, after signing the proper consent form (see Appendix D), she agreed to be interviewed. The data from this interview was only used to better understand the student response and classroom environment.

Classroom Environment

All the participants were taught by the same instructor but were from two different classrooms. Given the physical distancing requirements, each class was divided in two sections, each containing half of the students. Thus, participants in this study were part of one of four possible classroom cohorts. Each section attended classes online every second day. Alternating between online and in-person attendance over the course of the nine-day schedule allowed for an equal amount of time in-school versus at home. However, given that physics classes occur only four times in the nine-day schedule, some weeks, students were either completely online or in-person for their physics classes. Moreover, according to the interviewed participants, only math, chemistry and physics required the students to attend lectures remotely during the days their sections were at home. This allowed for more time to catch up on homework and complete the extra assigned work from the other courses.

Procedure

Data was obtained in three ways: in-depth interviews, two student surveys and in-class observations – for the first two months of class only as I was no longer allowed to visit the high school due to additional COVID-19 restrictions. The first survey was sent to the participants via email on October 8th, 2020 as a Microsoft Office form (see Appendix E). This survey was used to determine the participants' initial interest in taking the course, their expectations for the course, as well as their usual behavior in and outside of class when online and in-person. The survey also asked the participants their preferred learning and studying methods for physics as well as their initial thoughts on the advantages and disadvantages to online versus face-to-face classes. Additionally, a demographics section was used to determine the gender, academic standing, and preferred learning type of each participant, as well as their willingness to participate in the interview process. The second survey was sent via email on December 30th, 2020, as a second Microsoft Office form (see Appendix F). The second survey was used to see if there were any differences in the participants' opinion of the course, academic standing, as well as in their study and learning methods after three months of blended learning. The survey was used to determine the participants' satisfaction based on their grades, interest, and time commitment, as well as the classwork's usefulness and clarity. Participants were also asked to compare the quality of their education based on its delivery method, i.e., online versus face-to-face, and how each method compared. Moreover, participants were asked to share what they thought was more stressful about

the school year so far and how they would improve the way the class was taught. The objective was to obtain information about how the students' engagement and motivation had changed over the first half of the year.

In-depth interviews were conducted around the December holiday break with the participants who volunteered. The interviews were semi-structured, following an interview guide (see Appendix G) and each lasted between 45 to 60 minutes. The purpose of the interview process was to provide a deeper insight into questions that were asked in the surveys and see what was truly important to the students. The interviews also served to ensure trustworthiness, enabling comparisons to be made between the survey data and in-class observations. The interviews also served to fill in any pertinent information that might have been missed in the surveys due to a lack of questions pertaining to said topic. The teacher was also interviewed following a second interview guide (see Appendix H), in order to provide insight on the instructor's perspective, as well as to contextualize students' responses from the surveys and interviews. The teacher interview was conducted on October 1st and had a duration of 45 minutes. This interview was also used to better understand the transition between face-to-face teaching to online and mixed education, as well as the changes made to the course content, presentation and classroom environment given the new restrictions.

The in-class observations were conducted during each class from September to early-November, for a total of about 23 hours. These observations were recorded in a field-journal. The notes focused on the interaction between the students and the teachers present in-class and online, the lesson plans and what was done during class time, as well as the student-student in-class interaction. The purpose of these observations was to provide context for the data provided by both the surveys and the interviews. It is important to note that since the physics teacher also taught a chemistry class and Grade 10 science, I was also able to observe these classes to gain a greater perspective on the teacher's overall teaching methods and style. Overall, collecting data using interviews, surveys and observation was done to avoid the limitations due to relying on one specific method of data collection (Maxwell, 2013), and to obtain enough data to provide a more detailed understanding of the situation.

Data Trustworthiness

Data trustworthiness is often characterized by terms such as “*credibility, dependability, conformability, and transferability,*” (Elo et al., 2014). Credibility can be established using triangulation, where the same research questions are asked to different participants and data is collected from different sources (Devault, 2019). In this study this was done by collecting data using two different surveys, interviews and in-class observations. In her article, Devault (2019) explains that “transferability generalizes study findings and attempts to apply them to other situations and contexts. Researchers cannot prove definitively that outcomes based on the interpretation of the data are transferable, but they can establish that it is likely,” (Devault, 2019). In this case, considering the sample subjects’ characteristics is key. Since the study’s sample size is of 10 participants, the interpretation of the data is limited to this specific case study. By coding the interview data and comparing it to the survey data, the data was sorted as either idiographic or nomothetic. Idiographic analysis refers to the identification of themes that are unique to an individual, while nomothetic analysis refers to themes that appear to be shared across the sample (Ponterotto, 2005). Dependability is achieved in this study by providing “sufficient details and contextual information” (Devault, 2019) by being as detailed as possible in the writing of this report and adding all supporting material in the appendices. Moreover, the addition of all the forms, interview guides and surveys done in this study makes it more easily replicable, as everything that was used to collect the data is explicitly outlined. This is how confirmability was achieved for this case study.

Survey Data Analysis

Both surveys contained a mix of quantitative and qualitative questions. The data from the quantitative questions was tabulated and graphed by category as shown in the results section. Due to the small sample size, $n=10$, the quantitative data is analyzed as a case study rather than with statistics. The quantitative questions either asked the participants to select all the statements that they agreed with or to rank statements by order of preference (see Appendix E & Appendix F). The data from these questions was then used to inform the coding of the interviews. The qualitative questions from the first survey mainly asked the students to name the advantages and challenges of each learning mode, while those in the second one additionally inquired about the students’ experience and opinion. The latter were added to give the opportunity for the non-interviewed participants to voice their experience with fewer limitations than the quantitative questions,

providing a greater contextual understanding and increasing the possibility of categorizing data as either idiographic or nomothetic. The qualitative data was organized by category and then coded. For example, in the second survey students were asked to explain the differences between their learning experience online versus in-person. Each participant wrote a few sentences, so each line was examined and categorized. As part of their response, one student wrote: “We are not the teacher’s main focus while online. We cannot see her visual demonstrations,” which was coded as the *lack of student-teacher interaction* theme. Themes were then combined into larger categories and *lack of student-teacher interaction* was linked to the greater theme of *isolation*. Each greater category had previously been defined in the literature. Both qualitative and quantitative questions were used to code the interview data and detect potential inconsistencies between participants’ declarations. In the end, no major inconsistencies were noted between the survey and interview data.

Interview Data Analysis

As each interview was video and audio recorded, the first step in its analysis was to transcribe each interview in Word documents. These interviews were then read, and individually coded line-by-line based on themes highlighted in the survey data as explained above. After coding each interview, I went back over some interviews to add any newfound codes before combining all the themes into a coding structure and then refining those into larger categories. For example, the statement: “It’s definitely a challenging course and that’s why I feel like it’s very motivating because everyone knows it’s challenging so we all feel the need to help each other out,” was coded as *cooperation based on collective struggle* which was then related to the broader theme of *community*. Much like the qualitative survey data analysis, the interview data analysis was guided by the objectives of this study, which were to investigate students’ experience with mixed online learning, perceived barriers and facilitators to engagement, and satisfaction of their psychological needs. Essentially, the objectives of this study were used to create organizational categories based on literature prior to the data collection to structure the categories derived from the participants’ experiences known as substantive categories (Maxwell, 2013). Therefore, the broader theme of *community* from the aforementioned example was integrated in the *facilitator* organizational category. This analytical process formed hierarchical coding structures as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Example of Partial Hierarchical Coding Structure

Note: Top level represents an organizational category, the second level represents substantive categories, third represents themes and the bottom level represents participant quotes.

It is important to note that the interviews were repeatedly compared to one another throughout the coding process. Exactly like the qualitative survey data analysis, the data was analyzed both ideographically and nomothetically (Ponterotto, 2005) to classify the data as either

shared across the sample, or unique to a participant. For example, since only one student mentioned *ability to fidget without distracting others* as an advantage of online learning, it was coded as an idiographic theme. Conversely, since all participants mentioned *greater distractions* when attending lectures online, the theme was coded as being nomothetic. According to Ponterotto (2005), this distinction provides a richer understanding of participants' experiences.

Observational Data

The observational data was primarily used to detect inconsistencies between the survey and interview data, relative to the actual classroom environment and student behaviour. No major inconsistencies were found. Observations were also used to inform the coding themes used for the interview and qualitative survey question analysis. Specifically, the field notes were used to confirm that the categories and themes were contextually relevant to the course. Moreover, the classroom observations helped to better understand the participants' anecdotal accounts. For example, if a student mentioned finding a specific lab more helpful than another, the field notes would help in defining the specifics of each lab and help better interpret the student's statement.

RESULTS

The study results are presented in eight separate sections, reflecting the following organizational categories: (1) social interactions, (2) administrative/instructor issues, (3) academic/technical skills, (4) learner motivation & satisfaction, (5) time and support for studies, (6) technology, (7) learning environment, and (8) physics learning requirements. The organizational categories were based on categories used in a study on student barriers to online learning by Muilenburg & Berge (2005), as well as the factors that affect engagement determined by Newman (1989). These barriers and factors were adapted to better fit this study. The teacher's point of view and experiences were added to each section to better contextualize the student data.

Social interactions

Themes under this category include interaction/communication between teacher and students, interaction/communication among students, isolation, and student collaboration.

During the first survey, all students answered that they keep their cameras off during online lectures, except if asked to turn it on. In the same survey, all students also said that it was easier to participate, ask questions and get help when classes were in person. Four students said they prefer learning and working on their own, while the rest answered that they preferred to work in small groups of 2-4 people.

During the interviews, all the students mentioned that during online classes there was very little interaction between the teacher and the students, and among students. As one student mentioned: "At school I pay more attention and participate because the teacher can see us and she makes sure we're understanding. Online it's easy to lose interest because the teacher is just reading slides and not paying attention to us." Another said that success with online education "depends on how you deal with isolation. My friend with anxiety really struggles with the online portion, she needs the social aspect of school." Isolation was a theme mentioned by all students across both surveys as a disadvantage to online learning. When asked to clarify this, one of the interviewed students said: "Right now [because of COVID-19 restrictions], we can't do anything, we can't go see our friends or go out to do something so it's all very isolating. I think if school was online, but we were allowed to go out anytime and see people it wouldn't be as bad." When asked how she would teach a class in that scenario, the student mentioned that she would include games "like Kahoot" every class and make students do "in-class group projects." When discussing current class

participation another interviewed student mentioned that except for texts between her and her friends during class, there was no student participation, “except maybe when someone asks a question but that doesn’t really happen much.” She explained that there was no back and forth interaction between the teacher and the student, and no discussion either. When asked why she thought this was the case, her answer was that “the teacher is very structured, like it feels like we have to cover as much of the notes and examples as possible so that’s kind of all that we do... There’s not a lot of time to talk about things we kind of just have to try to understand as much as we can.” When asked if the students helped each other out, all the interviewees mentioned that there was a strong sense of community outside of class. As one student mentioned: “I feel like all the students in my class, we’re all very connected. Like whenever there’s a problem we all help each other. We’re kind of a little community I guess. [...] Everyone knows it’s challenging, so we know all need to help each other out.”

In the first survey, questions 5-9 related to student social behavior during, and after both online and in-person classes (see Figure 4 and Figure 5). These graphs help to compare student participation and interaction in online and face-to-face settings.

From the teacher’s perspective, the social interactions were the hardest part to do in the simultaneous blended model. As she mentioned:

When everything was online, I was home with my two-screen set up and I could focus on the students and check the chat and my email since everything was on my screens. Some of the students are shy about not knowing, so when everything was online, I could answer their questions directly in the way that they preferred. It’s much easier than being here and having two different things to manage and making sure that everything is going smoothly and that everyone is following. Now, I only have my laptop so it’s impossible to have the notes and the students both on my screen and also try to pay attention to emails, and the chat and the in-person questions.” When asked about student participation online, she said that she really missed it because she doesn’t have enough screens to see the students and be able “to see how they react and what feelings they have about the content like I can when they’re in class.” As she added on: “If I had good equipment like an extra monitor where I could see all their faces, and their questions that would be great but right now the screen that I work with is essentially what the board is. It’s where I have the class notes and where I write on and teach.” The teacher mentioned having to “check

on their work and check in with them all the time” when they are online because online she teaches more and hears them less. As she explains:

Let's say I explain something, I always look around and when I see that they look uneasy, I slow down, and I ask them where I've lost them, and they bring me back. When I'm online, I would go through one sentence in the notes, and stop to ask: “are you okay?” if they are, I move on and if not, I would explain, and then I would do another sentence and stop, and repeat that process. So, when I'm online I stop a lot more than when I'm in person because when I'm in person I can just look at their faces and occasionally check in, online I have to keep asking because if not no one stops me even if they are lost.

Figure 4

Student Social Behavior During Class

Note: Data from questions 5-6 from the first student survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Figure 5

Student Social Behavior After Class

Note: Data from questions 8-9 from the first student survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Administrative / Teacher Issues

Themes under this category include course material delivery, assigned workload, ability to teach online, clarity of expectations/instructions, feedback from teacher, access to teacher, and the quality of instruction online.

All students mentioned the overall greater workload and difficulty in their courses relative to the previous year. When asked about this in the interviews, all five students said that, in general, while there was more assigned work, and the work was generally harder than what it had been the year before, the workload specifically for physics was “manageable” and that they had enough time and help to complete everything. In the surveys however, two students felt overwhelmed by the workload, with one saying that “the fact that the curriculum hasn't change due to the pandemic is ridiculous. We have to learn the same material as if we were in the classroom everyday which we obviously aren't and rather than focusing on having students understand the work we're having homework constantly piled onto our backs.” That being said, all of the interviewed students mentioned how the physics teacher encouraged the students to reach out to her if they had any difficulty, and that she was willing to do “one-on-one Zoom sessions if we really needed it.” Another major complaint was not being able to see the instructor during online classes. During the interviews, one of the students mentioned that since the teacher had to teach in-person and online simultaneously, she would often walk out of the frame or “forget” about the online students.” As one student put: “Sometimes she would do a demonstration for the kids in class but her computer faces the wall so we would miss most of it and barely hear anything.” Students also mentioned that for all their classes, teachers seemed more “dull and sad” when teaching online since they couldn't see the students.

In the second survey, students were asked about what they would change about the course if they taught it. The most mentioned change, according to six students, was to spend more time on making sure the students understand a topic the first time, rather than review it multiple times. As one student put:

I would not move on further in the topic before the students understand what you first taught. Our teachers seem to be on a tight schedule [...] and often moved on when most

students didn't understand claiming we'd review later, leaving many of us to learn things right before the test. [...] I found that during some topics we spent 30 minutes reviewing what we did within the last 3 classes before learning something new and we reviewed the same things every class. It felt like a waste of time because we heard this exact information yesterday. It also didn't help those who didn't understand because she wouldn't explain but just reread what was written on the sheets.

Three other students mentioned doing less reviewing in class and to slow down the pace during lectures. One student mentioned not providing the answers immediately with the assignments since it "gives the students an easy way out of doing work," this student added: "Personally I know I shouldn't be just taking answers but sometimes when you don't understand that's easier than figuring it out." Another student mentioned it would be helpful to provide lesson plans ahead of time, so that students could better prepare for the class, while another said they would like to have more detailed notes, "so they are elaborating the formulas in a clearer way." Having more labs and hands-on material, longer in-class work periods and "going over questions with the whole class that most students get wrong in the practice sheets," were also mentioned by individual students. In the second survey, question 3 asked student their thoughts on the teacher's clarity. Eight student thought that the teacher took the students' perspectives into account and explained why she had them perform certain activities or made certain decisions. Eight students also agreed that the teacher gave them enough time to complete assignments. The fifth question in the second survey asked the participants' experiences with the course's grading structure (see Figure 6).

From the teacher's perspective, the switch to simultaneous blended education forced her to use notes written on Word when teaching instead of her usual method so that both online and in-person students could follow along the notes at the same time, either on their screens or seeing them projected on the board. Additionally, labs had to be done during the in-person sessions since they required specific material. Originally, she had tried to film and take pictures of the labs so that online students could do it at the same time as their face-to-face peers, but that students found it too difficult and asked her to change it.

Figure 6

Student Perspective on course grading structure

Note: Data from question 5 from the second student survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Academic & Technical Skills

Themes under this category include communication skills for online learning, reading skills for online learning, shy or lack of confidence for online learning, and the development of skills due to online learning.

The most common skills required to succeed with online education according to the students were: time-management, independent learning, and having the motivation to stay focused in class and the confidence to ask questions even if it “feels more awkward.” One student mentioned that the most stressful part of the year was “adapting to learning on my own. There have been many times when I have to take a couple hours to look through all my problems and notes just to answer my own questions.” Additionally, students found asking questions via email was difficult because it was much harder to understand the teacher’s answer rather than if it was in person. In the second survey, six students also mentioned the importance of being organized, whether it was in keeping track of the school schedule, or in keeping all notes and assignments sorted and completed on time.

In the second survey, students were asked to explain how their preferred learning type affected their learning experience online and in-person. Overall, students mentioned that online

classes are predominantly auditory based, while in-person classes had significantly more visual and “hands-on” elements. All the students who identified themselves as more hands-on i.e., kinesthetic, or visual learners, said they had “trouble understanding and focusing online” and missed the experience of doing labs.

Learner Motivation & Satisfaction

Themes under this category include motivation to take the course, personal motivation for online learning, responsibility for learning, and stressors.

In the first survey, when students were asked why they had chosen to take physics, eight students mentioned that having physics knowledge would help them be more successful, six students thought that learning physics is fun, five said that they planned on pursuing a career that involves knowing physics, three students mentioned that they think physics knowledge is important to have in life, three students mentioned parents telling them to take the course, and two students mentioned taking the course for other reasons (see Figure 7). Students’ perception of the course over time was done by asking them in both the first and second survey if they thought course was or was going to be challenging, interesting, time-consuming, fun, and motivating (see Figure 8). Questions 3-4 of the first survey were also used to determine the students’ behavior before both online and in-person classes (See Figure 9).

Figure 7

Students’ Reasons for Taking Physics Course

Note: Data from question 1 of the first survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Figure 8

Students' Perceptions of the Physics Course

Note: Data taken from question 2 of the first survey, and second survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Figure 9

Student Behavior Before Online and In-Person Classes

Note: Data taken from question 3 of the first survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

In the second student survey, question 1 was used to determine students' satisfaction based on amount of knowledge and understanding gained, as well as overall satisfaction with the course (see Figure 10).

Figure 10

Student Satisfaction

Note: Data taken from question 1 of the second survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

In the second survey, students also mentioned that without the more structured school routine, and the teacher to keep them on task, many found it easier to procrastinate and were less motivated to learn online. As one student mentioned: “Online there is no one to keep you in check so you need to develop a certain level of maturity to be able to focus.” Overall, technical difficulties, lack of social interactions and structure lowered the majority of the students’ motivation to attend classes. Additionally, when students were asked to explain the most stressful part of the school year, seven mentioned the greater workload and difficulty, four mentioned being stressed about getting grades high enough to get accepted in their program of choice in CEGEP, and three students mentioned adapting to online learning was stressful. In the second survey, students were also questioned about their perception of learning online versus in-person (see Figure 11).

Figure 11

Student Perceptions of Online Learning

Note: Data taken from question 6 of the second survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Time & Support for Studies

Themes under this category include personal time, schedule flexibility, and support from friends & family.

The second most mentioned advantage of online classes according to the students was the schedule flexibility and the increase in personal time since there was no need to travel to school. On days where students attended classes online, they finished at noon, giving them extra time for studying, part-time jobs and extracurricular activities. Schedule flexibility was mentioned by six students in the first survey and three students in the second survey, while saving time online was mentioned by seven students in the first survey and by six students in the second. Schedule flexibility was described by a student as the ability to be “working in a particular class even after it ends when I’m home,” while another student wrote: “if you don’t feel like doing work right after class you can do it later. Like in class they give you time but sometimes you just waste it because you’re not in the mood.” Students also described having the greater freedom to learn at their own pace and study on their own time when having classes online. Additionally, three students mentioned having greater access to resources and support when online since they could refer to

their parents, friends and the Internet while simultaneously attending class. This allowed them to “multitask” and “answer each other’s questions” without disturbing the class. In the first survey, nine students said that they would ask the teacher for help if they had any questions about the physics material, eight students said that they would ask their friends and classmates, four students would ask their parents and one student would ask a tutor. In the second survey, students were asked to compare how much time they spent on physics material compared to material for other classes, if they had enough time to complete assignments, and if they think it was an appropriate amount of time (See Figure 12).

From the teacher’s perspective, online learning made it more difficult to reach students and support them: “when they have drama problems at home, it's difficult to reach them. You try to phone them, but you never get an answer, so it's difficult to reach the real person inside of them and say: ‘look I really want you to keep going,’” When asked how the teacher tried to mitigate the situation she explained that she would send emails and phone calls until she got an answer and then she would show the students one-on-one how to connect and reach out if they had any issues. For understanding issues during class, she would continuously check-in with the students and then offer one-on-one sessions after class to help those who had trouble understanding.

Figure 12

Student Perceptions on their Time Spent on Physics Coursework

Note: Data taken from question 4 of the second survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Technology

Themes under this category include Internet connectivity, technology failures, and material access.

In the first survey, three students mentioned that an advantage of online classes was that “you don’t have to worry about forgetting books or needing a pencil.” Two students also commented on the fact that since all the course materials were posted online, they were accessible at any time.

However, all students mentioned that a disadvantage with online classes were technical problems such as bad Internet connections, links not working and frozen screens hindered their learning. One student reported that “many Internet problems made it so that I couldn’t listen to the class.” During the interview, one student mentioned that a lot of time was spent waiting for teachers to fix technical difficulties and waiting on students to connect to the Zoom meetings. She also mentioned that since the teacher shares her screen, she felt like there was no point in paying attention since “half the time the notes are frozen so you can’t see what she’s talking about, and when she writes on the screen it’s not very clear, so you spend more time just trying to figure out what it means instead of paying attention.”

From the instructor’s perspective, technological issues were one of her biggest worries. For every class she would start the online session at least five minutes early to make sure everyone would be able to connect. She said that she “would maybe need another computer with my email open so that I can see if students have tried to email me while I’m teaching so that I can help them,” but that doing so would be “a lot to manage since I already have to teach the students that are in class too.” The teacher mentioned that when everything was online, she could manage to do so with her set-up at home and that it was much easier since she was in her element and “not being distracted with people around me.” She also mentioned that with only her laptop in class, having everyone’s camera on was an issue because she didn’t have enough screen space for both the online students’ faces and her work. The teacher also mentioned that correcting students’ work online was difficult because it required special equipment to be able to write on the online copies. Without this equipment, she had to send each student an email explaining where they went wrong, which was time consuming and often confusing for the students.

Learning Environment

Themes under this category include comfort, noise levels, distractions, safety, workspace area, and attendance type.

In the first survey, nine out of ten students preferred attending classes in-person rather than online. At the end of the semester, students were asked to rank their preferred method of attendance between all in-person, all online or in the half/half model they had experienced over the course of the semester (see Figure 13). Overall, the majority of students preferred attending classes all in-person, but the half/half model was ranked closely second.

Figure 13

Students' Preferred Method of Attendance

Note: For each response, the category ranked first was assigned a value of 3, the one ranked second a value of 2, and last one a value of 1. The total for each attendance was then calculated and then ranked as shown in this graph.

Comfort was the most mentioned advantage to online learning, expressed by eight students in the first survey, and four students in the second survey – despite the questions asked for them to mention new advantages. Students enjoyed being in their “own environment”, oftentimes with a “bigger workspace”. One student said: “I don’t have to be seated all class, I can pace my room, stationary pedal and fidget without having to worry about disturbing others”. Comfort was also equated to the lack of dress code, lack of designated eating time and “less peer pressure”. In the first survey, three students also expressed feeling safer from the virus when they stayed home. In the second survey, the most mentioned advantage of online classes was having a less noisy environment or one without distractions from peers. As one student wrote: “People can’t talk over the teacher since we’re all muted”. Students mentioned that having a quieter environment helped

with their concentration. Additionally, three students mentioned that it was easier to do assignments and tests when the course was online.

However, while being at home meant less distractions from peers, eight students mentioned that with “no one to keep you in check” it was easy to be distracted. One student mentioned that “online it can be hard to concentrate, I’m at home, I’m comfortable so I doze off more”, while another mentioned: “sometimes I spend the whole class cleaning my room and realize later that I didn’t listen at all.” Students also brought up the fact that school provides an escape from a possibly toxic household.

In the first survey, students were asked to rank the place where they best studied and worked on assignments between public spaces (i.e., cafeteria, coffee shop, park), the library, at home, or during in-class work periods (see Figure 14). There was a clear preference for studying and working on assignments at home.

Figure 14

Students’ Preferred Work and Study Area

Note: For each response, the category ranked first was assigned a value of 4, the one ranked second a value of 3, the third a value of 2, and last one a value of 1. The total for each attendance was then calculated and then ranked as shown in this graph.

Physics Learning Methods & Understanding

Themes under this category include study method preferences and learning method preferences, limitations of learning methods, and building understanding.

In the first survey, question 10 asked which method they needed to learn physics (see Figure 15), while in the second survey, questions 13 and 14 asked students to rank the method that makes them understand the material the most during class, and while studying, respectively (see Figure 16 & Figure 17).

Figure 15

Methods Needed to Learn Physics Ranked by Students

Note: Data taken from question 10 of the first survey. Values represent number of students who agreed with the statement.

Figure 16

Methods Needed for Understanding Course Material in Class Ranked by Students

Note: Data taken from question 13 of the second survey. For each response, the category ranked first was assigned a value of 9 and the last one a value of 1. The total for each category was then calculated and ranked as shown in this graph.

Figure 17

Methods Needed for Understanding Course Material while Studying Ranked by Students

Note: Data taken from question 14 of the second survey. For each response, the category ranked first was assigned a value of 9 and the last one a value of 1. The total for each category was then calculated and ranked as shown in this graph.

In the interviews, four out of the five students said they didn't really see the purpose in learning vectors. As one student said: "Like I understand that it's a value with a direction, or like a line of a certain length with an angle, but I can't see how I'll ever need to apply them in real life." Similarly, another mentioned that "unless you have a job doing math or like engineering, I'm pretty sure we're never going to use vectors again." When asked how they learned and studied, these four students mentioned that having the teacher "show them how to do things" and then re-reading the notes and doing the problems until every step made sense was the way they learned. Conversely, the one student who thought everything they were learning was useful was because "it's not about the stuff that you're learning, it's about the logic behind it, like it's teaching you how to think." When asked if there was anything that they were learning that weren't useful she said:

I think it's like, I see physics in the real world and the more I learn about it, the more I see it in the real world. Like I was going sledding with my family and I was like you should

put your weight there or like, I don't know, it just felt nice to kind of understand like the vectors. And it's like I can definitely see it in the real world and see that it is useful.

When asked about her study habits, this student replied:

At the beginning of the course, I would go to make cue cards and ask more questions if I didn't understand something. But now I've fallen back on just like practicing and doing the same question over and over and by working backwards, so that I understand the question and just go off that.

When asked when the shift happened and why she answered:

Right before the physics exam [in December]... I think it probably has to do with the whole online kind of teaching and like it's weirder to ask questions when you know the whole class is going to be listening to you. So, it's easier to figure out by yourself. And I guess like I don't completely understand physics well enough to be making cue cards and repeating that stuff because it could just mean nothing to me. And I guess there's more logic, more math, behind it now than there was at the beginning of the year, so the questions are just more problems so if I remember how to do those it works.

DISCUSSION

The goal of this study was to investigate the experience of high school students enrolled in a synchronous hybrid physics classroom. Specifically, it aimed to identify the factors and barriers perceived by the students that contributed to their engagement in the classroom while online and in-person. As expressed in previous research, factors affecting engagement were students' need for competence, extrinsic rewards, intrinsic interest, social support and sense of ownership (Newman, 1989), while barriers to online engagement were related to social interactions, technical aspects, prerequisite skills, motivation, infrastructure/support services and time (Muilenburg & Berge, 2005).

Overall, each category – (1) social interactions, (2) administrative/instructor issues, (3) academic/technical skills, (4) learner motivation & satisfaction, (5) time and support for studies, (6) technology, (7) learning environment, and (8) physics learning requirements – contained both perceived barriers and facilitators contributing to student engagement. Additionally, there was some overlap between categories, as a barrier in one category was the reason for a barrier in another. For example, the lack of proper technical equipment, namely the number of screens the teacher could use, was the main cause for the lack of teacher-student interactions when students were online.

In the *social interactions* category, the main barriers to student engagement were caused by being online. All students equated being online with isolation, lack of student-student interaction, lack of student-teacher interaction and feeling awkward about participating in class. That being said, all of these barriers could be overcome by adjusting the course delivery to be more student-centred. In this case the perceived barriers are not necessarily caused by being online, but rather due to the lesson plan structure. For example, in a more student-centred classroom students could increase their participation through collaborative groupwork and discussion, giving them the opportunity to interact with one another and have the teacher lead the group discussions rather than present the material. Peers could learn from each other rather than rely on the teacher. When asked how they would improve the class, students also mentioned using educational game apps like Kahoot, and having more in-class group projects. Interestingly, despite the lack of student-student interaction in class, many students mentioned feeling more connected to the students in their section. According to one student, they created a group messaging chat and continuously helped

each other, even during classes. Students found that the sense of community within their sections was motivating.

For the *administrative/teacher issues* category, the main barriers were related to the amount and difficulty of the students' general workload. While most student mentioned that the workload specifically for physics was manageable since the teacher gave them ample time and support to complete the assigned work, many found it difficult to learn since it was their first-time learning physics. Overall, the larger workload was associated with being online since classes other than math, chemistry and physics did not provide online lectures, and instead relied on the student to catch up on the extra material on the days they stayed home. Other often mentioned barriers were the pace of the physics lectures, students felt as though there was not enough time to process the amount of material they were learning in each lecture, this was found to be independent from classes being online. Additionally, students felt that a lot of time was "wasted" by reviewing material from previous classes, with all of them saying they would have preferred to use that time to make sure everyone was understanding a topic before moving on. That being said, independently of the mode of education, students were happy that the teacher took their perspectives into account and adjusted the content delivery accordingly. They were also satisfied by the amount of time they were given to complete homework, in the fairness of the course's grading structure and in the teacher's clarity of expectations and instructions.

When it came down to breaking down the needed *academic & technical skills* to succeed in online learning, students agreed that it required good time-management skills, independent learning, confidence to participate, organization and intrinsic motivation. Good time-management and organization was required to be able to prioritize assignments from all their classes and successfully complete them in the time they had. Many students agreed that while online learning gave them more personal time, without those skills and intrinsic motivation it was easy to procrastinate and get distracted. That being said, about half the students reported that because of the online delivery portion of the course, they had significantly improved these skills. One student mentioned that while it was initially difficult and a lot of hard work, she felt much better prepared for future "harder" studies than she had been in previous years. The most significant barrier related to skills and online learning was that the online delivery was mainly auditory based. Students reported that with technical difficulties like screens freezing,

they often had to rely on what the teacher was saying to learn since the visual material was not keeping up. Additionally, learning remotely left students without any sort of hands-on component to learn from. Many students ranked in-person learning above the half/half model because it entailed a more balanced learning experience in terms of auditory, visual and kinetic content.

In terms of the student's overall *motivation & satisfaction*, the majority of students were satisfied with their decision to take physics, and they were happy with the amount of knowledge they had gained from the course. However, almost all the students found that many of the topics they were learning were not applicable in their daily life, with some mentioning they felt as though the time spent learning these topics could have been spent elsewhere. Conversely, others were "okay" with having learned these topics because it was "teaching [them] how to learn." Figure 11 shows that only two out of ten students felt that the quality of education was the same when attending online compared to attending classes in person. Overall, students felt more motivated to attend classes in-person due to the lack of technical difficulties, and the greater number of social interactions. Many also found that the more structured school environment and the pressure of the teacher made attending classes face-to-face more productive as it was harder to procrastinate, sleep, and provided less distraction than their home environment. It was interesting to note that nine out of ten students felt that had similar experiences with online learning as their classmates. Additionally, in terms of defining the most stressful parts of the semester, the majority of students mentioned the greater workload and difficulty due to online learning, as well as the adaptation to online learning. Independent to learning remotely, students were also stressed by having to achieve grades high enough to get accepted in their program of choice at CEGEP.

Relative to the *time & support* for their studies, students preferred the online learning delivery as it allowed for more schedule flexibility, an increase in personal time, and more freedom to learn at their own pace. Students felt that they could sleep more, eat when they were hungry (even if in class), and "actually have time to do stuff [they] wanted." As one of the interviewed students mentioned: "if classes were all in-person I would definitely not have enough time to have my part-time job and still have time to do well in school and take breaks to do workouts and hang out with my family." Additionally, students felt they had better access to resources when learning at home. As one student mentioned: "At home you can ask your parents, text your friends and go look things up on the Internet whenever you want which is nice." That being said, overall students

felt that it was hard to connect with the teacher if they needed help, and that during lectures it often felt like the teacher “forgot” about the online students.

Issues with *technology* was one of the biggest barriers to online learning. Students felt as though technical issues like the internet not working, screens freezing and links not working severely disrupted class time and their motivation to keep attending online lectures. Even the teacher reported that if she had better equipment, such as a proper computer set-up in the classroom, the quality of the education would be significantly better as it would allow her to actually see the online students and better connect with them. According to students, the biggest advantage about being online, excluding the ones mentioned in other categories, was that they didn't have to worry about forgetting materials like books, and pencils.

Overall, students ranked their preference of *learning environment* as in-person, half/half, and online, in order from best to worst. The most mentioned advantages of online learning mainly related to the students' comfort as being online allowed them to have bigger workspaces, a quieter environment, and a space of their own. Students felt that online there was less peer pressure, they could eat whenever they wanted and not have to worry about disturbing their peers while fidgeting. Students also felt safer from the COVID-19 virus at home and that overall, it was easier to work on assignments in their own space. Downsides of staying home were that it was easier to fall asleep or be distracted as there was no one to “keep them in check”. Additionally, a couple of students mentioned that school provides an escape from a possibly toxic household and that being stuck to learn online in such an environment would be very challenging and possibly dangerous. In the second survey, six out of ten students indicated that their opinion about taking an online course had changed. When asked about this during the interviews, one student explained that she was initially very reluctant to learn online since the previous year the online classes had been very disorganized and overall “not really useful”. She further explained that over the course of this semester, she realized that online learning allowed for a more flexible schedule, giving her the time to have a part-time job and still finish all her homework.

Lastly, this study showed that the students' *learning methods* for physics mainly relied on problem solving. Initially, students reported that the best way to learn physics for them was by doing as many practice problems as they could, see demonstrations, and read the textbook and the notes, in order from most useful. During the second survey, student replied that in class, listening to the teacher in-person, having the teacher solve example problems and then having someone

other than the teacher explain the concepts was most beneficial to them. At home while studying, students indicated that the top three methods they used to understand the material was by solving as many problems as possible, re-reading the textbook and the notes, and explaining what they understood to someone else, demonstrating that students relied on more memorization-based study methods rather than focusing on understanding. It is important to note that there was a significant disconnect between theories learned in class and how students could relate them to the real world. During the interviews, only one student was able to explain how she understood the way the physics concepts related to one another and to the way she understood what she saw around her. This student also mentioned initially focusing her attention on understanding the concepts while studying and then switching to a more memorization-based method before exams because that's what was being tested. At the end, she realised that even if she didn't fully understand, if she solved a lot of problems and remembered the steps, she was successful on the tests. Interestingly, all other interviewed students mentioned using this latter study method, explaining that if they remembered the notes and the steps to solve the problems, they were successful during the tests. This brings up a significant flaw in our current education model, as students are more inclined to memorize or "cram and regurgitate" what they learn instead of actually understanding it simply because that is what brings them the most success on tests at this level. All the interviewed students mentioned that they didn't feel that the tests were representative of their understanding. One student mentioned that she wished teachers left a blank page at the back so that she could write all the stuff that she did understand, but that wasn't tested in the other questions. She also felt as though it would be "more fair to have a variety of questions" – like multiple choice, short answer, long answer and problem-solving based – as some students don't test well on specific kinds of questions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, barriers to online learning are mainly due to technological issues as they impact the amount of time and the quality of the provided education which in turn affects the students' motivation. The quality of the equipment used to teach severely impacts the teachers' ability to connect with remote students and the amount of possible social interactions. The other main barriers of online education are related to the skills deemed by the students as required in order successfully learn remotely. In general, these skills are required to succeed in school, but students felt as though being online really emphasized their need to master time-management, independent learning, organization, intrinsic motivation and confidence. Overall, with a course delivery based on student-learning – including collaborative group work, discussion and educational games – learning online would allow students to be engaged and still enjoy the benefits of being in their own environment and having a more flexible schedule. The biggest barrier to overcome would be to provide hands-on experience to the students learning remotely. As one student mentioned, “online school would be awesome if we could go see our friends and go do activities like we did before the pandemic, and then just go to school sometimes to do labs.” In the end, with a curriculum focused on student participation and collaboration, the only perceived barriers to online learning are issues with technology and a lack of hands-on activities.

As a greater concerning matter, future studies could look into finding alternative ways to test student understanding. While student understanding was not originally a main focus of this study, it is important to note that students demonstrated that they were more inclined to memorize the material rather than to understand it. This was because it was easier to do while still allowing them to be successful on tests and exams, regardless if the course delivery was online or face-to-face.

REFERENCES

- Alghamdi, A., Karpinski, A.C., Lepp, A., & Barkley, J. (2020). Online and face-to-face classroom multitasking and academic performance: Moderated mediation with self-efficacy for self-regulated learning and gender. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 102, 214-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.08.018>
- Baskin, C. (2001). The Titanic, Volkswagens and collaborative group work: Remaking old favourites with new learning technologies. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 17(3), 265-278. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1795>
- Bronca, T. (2020, April 8). *COVID-19: A Canadian timeline: A look back at how the novel coronavirus began its spread across the nation and how our healthcare leaders responded*. Canadian Healthcare Network. <https://www.canadianhealthcarenetwork.ca/covid-19-a-canadian-timeline>
- Bell, J., Sawaya, S., & Cain, W. (2014). Synchromodal classes: Designing for shared learning experiences between face-to-face and online students. *International Journal of Designs for Learning*, 5(1), 68-82. <https://doi.org/10.14434/ijdl.v5i1.12657>
- Chen, N., & Zimitat, C. (2004). Differences in the quality of learning outcomes in a F2F blended versus wholly online course. In R. Atkinson, C. McBeath, D. Jonas-Dwyer, & R. Phillips (Eds), *Beyond the comfort zone: Proceedings of the 21st ASCILITE Conference* (pp. 175-179). ASCILITE. <http://www.ascilite.org.au/conferences/perth04/procs/chen.html>
- Devault, G. (2019, August 20). *Establishing trustworthiness in qualitative research*. The Balance Small Business. <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/establishing-trustworthiness-in-qualitative-research-2297042#:~:text=Qualitative%20research%20is%20important%20because,transferability%2C%20dependability%2C%20and%20confirmability.>

- El-Helou, J. & Kalman, C.S. (2018). Reflective writing for a better understanding of scientific concepts in high school. *The Physics Teacher*, 56, 88-91.
<https://doi.org/10.1119/1.5021434>
- Elo, S., Käärläonen, M., Kanste O., Pölkki, T., Utriainen K., & Kyngäs, H. (2014). Qualitative content analysis: A focus on trustworthiness. *Sage Open*, 4(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244014522633>
- Ferlazzo, L. (2021). *Strategies for teaching students online and face to face at the same time*. Education Week. https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/opinion-strategies-for-teaching-students-online-face-to-face-at-the-same-time/2021/02?fbclid=IwAR2SxGM9qLptyh_aWa2dKx4RDWIA3TIACF4LP5ILWxAgiCf0vrK0FYqBx0
- Freeman, L.A. (2013). Instructor time requirements to develop and teach online courses. *Proceedings of the 2013 AIS Siged: IAIM International Conference on Information Systems Education and Research*, 8. AIS eLibrary. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/siged2013/8>
- Harasim, L., Starr, L., Hiltz, R., Lucio, T., & Murray, T. (1996). A field guide to teaching and learning online. *Intelligent Tutoring Media*, 7(1), 34-35.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14626269609408367>
- Harasim, L. (2000). Shift happens: online education as a new paradigm in learning. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 3(1-2), 41-61. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516\(00\)00032-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516(00)00032-4)
- Haughey, M. (2005). Growth of online schooling in Canada. In C. Howard, J.V. Boettcher, & L. Justice (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Distance Learning* (Vol. 2, pp. 984-989). IGI Global.
https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CX3466600168/GVRL?u=sfu_z39&sid=GVRL&xid=2b509d2c
- Herrington J., & Oliver R. (2000). An instructional design framework for authentic learning

- environments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 48(3), 23-48.
- Hinkson, K., & Marchand, L. (2020, March 20). COVID-19 may keep Quebec students out of school until May, Legault says. *CBC News*.
<https://www.canadianhealthcarenetwork.ca/covid-19-a-canadian-timeline>
- Kalman, C.S. (2018). *Successful science and engineering teaching* (2nd ed.). Springer.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66140-7>
- Ladyshevsky, R.K. (2004). E-learning compared with face to face: differences in the academic achievement of postgraduate business students. *Australasian Journal of Education Technology*, 20(3), 316-336. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1350>
- Lightner, C.A., & Lightner-Laws, C.A. (2016). A blended model: simultaneously teaching a quantitative course traditionally, online and remotely. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 24(1), 224-238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2013.841262>
- Maxwell, J.A. (2013). Designing a Qualitative Study. In L. Bickerman & D.J. Rog (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Applied Social Research Methods* (2nd ed., pp. 214-253). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781483348858>
- Muilenburg, L.Y., & Berge, Z.L. (2005). Student barriers to online learning: A factor analytic study. *Distance Education*, 26(1), 29-48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587910500081269>
- Newmann, F.M. (1989). Student engagement and high school reform. *Educational Leadership*, 46(5), 34-36. http://www.ascd.org/ASCD/pdf/journals/ed_lead/el_198902_newmann.pdf
- Palloff, R.M., & Pratt, K. (2001). *Lessons from the cyberspace classroom: The realities of online teaching* (2nd ed.). Jossey-Bass.

Picciano, A.G., Seaman, J., Shea, P., & Swan, K. (2012). Examining the extent and nature of online learning in American K-12 education: The research initiatives of the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 15(2), 127-135.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2011.07.004>

Québec Ministère de l'Éducation (2020) Return to School: Plan
Approved by the Direction Générale de la Santé Publique [Brochure].
https://boardsite.lbpsb.qc.ca/Modules/FileManagement/files/Root/covid19/May/v13_017_napperon_retour-en-classe_ENG.pdf?fbclid=IwAR2akxBnlD6wBEkvwr77-8G5GoFx0lmyLGIFn29--e4TdkMoMx9Pf7bNC7c

Québec Ministère de l'Éducation. (2021). *Physics* (Publication No. 13-0023-025A).
Gouvernement du Québec.
http://www.education.gouv.qc.ca/fileadmin/site_web/documents/education/jeunes/pfeq/PFEQ_physique_EN.pdf

Roberge, J.F. (2020, August 10). To parents of students in preschool, elementary and secondary school [Press Release].
https://westwood.lbpsb.qc.ca/Portals/westwood/Documents/COVID/JR/ANG_2020_D-0510_20-00003_LM_rentree_Parents.pdf

Roseth, C., Akcaoglu, M., & Zellner, A. (2013). Blending synchronous face-to-face and computer-supported cooperative learning in a hybrid doctoral seminar. *TechTrends*, 57(3), 54-59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-013-0663-z>

van Schaik, P., Barker, P., & Beckstrand, S. (2003). A comparison of on-campus and online course delivery methods in Southern Nevada. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 40(1), 5-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1355800032000038859>

Stacey, E., & Wiesenberg F. (2007). A study of face-to-face and online teaching philosophies in Canada and Australia. *International Journal of Distance Education*, 22(1), 19-40.

Westwood Senior High School. (2020, March 17). Hey Westwood! We're thinking of you and sending you our best wishes to be healthy during this time of social [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/WestwoodSr/posts/503494757004693>

Westwood Senior High School. (2020, April 16). We are very happy to launch our Westwood Senior Academic Resources Website. This site is dedicated to providing your child [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/WestwoodSr/posts/521364578551044>

White, C.P., Ramirez, R., Smith, J.G., & Plonowski, L. (2010). Simultaneous delivery of a face-to-face course to on-campus and remote off-campus students. *Tech Trends*, 54(4), 34-40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-010-0418-z>

World Health Organization. (2020, June 29). *Listings of WHO's response to COVID-19*. <https://www.who.int/news/item/29-06-2020-covidtimeline>

Appendix A: Student Information and Consent Form

INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORM

Study Title: Impact on Student Learning of Online Physics Education

Researcher: Samantha CLARK

Researcher's Contact Information: samanthaclark55@gmail.com

Faculty Supervisor: Dr. Calvin KALMAN

Faculty Supervisor's Contact Information: calvin.kalman@concordia.ca

Source of funding for the study: N/A

You are being invited to participate in the research study mentioned above. This form provides information about what participating would mean. Please read it carefully before deciding if you want to participate or not. If there is anything you do not understand, or if you want more information, please ask me.

A. PURPOSE

The purpose of the research is to investigate the impact of online education on student learning and engagement. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the delivery of educational content had to quickly be adjusted in order to comply with guidelines put in place by authorities to reduce the infection spread. The goal of this project is to observe the impact of these new educational methods on both students and instructors, and to use these observations to propose a pedagogical model that is beneficial to all parties involved.

B. PROCEDURES

If you participate, you will be asked to fill out two surveys: one in the first weeks of classes and the second in the last two weeks before the winter holiday break. The surveys will be sent out by email as a Microsoft Office form. Both surveys should take about 15 minutes to complete. I will also ask you about your willingness to participate in the interview phase of the study. Choosing to participate in the interviews means that you will be interviewed for approximately 45 minutes, a week before or during the winter holiday break. The interview will take place over Zoom, outside of class time, and I will find a meeting time that fits your schedule. The audio and video data from the interviews will be recorded.

In total, participating in this study will less than an hour and a half if you participate in both surveys and in the interview process.

C. RISKS AND BENEFITS

There are no anticipated risks of the study.

You may or may not personally benefit from participating in this research. Your participation will contribute to a greater understanding of student-centered teaching and online learning pedagogical strategies.

D. CONFIDENTIALITY

We will gather the following information as part of this research: Your response to both surveys. If you participate in the interviews, we will also keep a recording of the interviews.

We will not allow anyone to access the information, except myself and my supervisor, which does not include the course instructor. We will only use the information for the purposes of the research described in this form. The gathered information will be coded. That means that the information will be identified by a code. I only will have a list that links the code to your name.

We will protect the information by keeping it on a password protected hard drive that only the investigators will have access to.

We intend to publish the results of the research. However, it will not be possible to identify you in the published results. We will destroy the information five years after the end of the study.

F. CONDITIONS OF PARTICIPATION

You do not have to participate in this research. It is purely your decision. If you do participate, you can withdraw at any time. Participation in this study will not affect your course grade in any way. You can also ask that the information you provided not be used, and your choice will be respected. If you decide to withdraw from the study, I need to be told within one month of the initial agreement and the data will be removed from the data set immediately after the confirmation of your withdrawal.

There are no negative consequences for not participating, stopping in the middle, or asking us not to use your information.

G. PARTICIPANT'S DECLARATION

I have read and understood this form. I have had the chance to ask questions and any questions have been answered. I agree to participate in this research under the conditions described.

NAME (please print):

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

If you have questions about the scientific or scholarly aspects of this research, please contact the researcher. Their contact information is on page I. You may also contact their faculty supervisor.

If you have concerns about ethical issues in this research, please contact the Manager, Research Ethics, Concordia University, 514.848.2424 ex. 7481 or oor.ethics@concordia.ca.

Appendix B: Parental Information and Consent Form

INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORM FOR PARENT OR LEGAL GUARDIAN

Study Title: Impact on Student Learning of Online Physics Education

Researcher: Samantha CLARK

Researcher's Contact Information: samanthaclark55@gmail.com

Faculty Supervisor: Dr. Calvin KALMAN

Faculty Supervisor's Contact Information: calvin.kalman@concordia.ca

Source of funding for the study: N/A

Your child is being invited to participate in the research study mentioned above. This form provides information about what participating would mean. Please read it carefully before deciding if you want your child to participate or not. If there is anything you do not understand, or if you want more information, please ask the researcher.

A. PURPOSE

The purpose of the research is to investigate the impact of online education on student learning and engagement. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the delivery of educational content had to quickly be adjusted in order to comply with guidelines put in place by authorities to reduce the infection spread. The goal of this project is to observe the impact of these new educational methods on both students and instructors, and to use these observations to propose a pedagogical model that is beneficial to all parties involved.

B. PROCEDURES

Your child will be asked to fill out two surveys: one in the first weeks of classes and the second in the last two weeks before the winter holiday break. The surveys will be sent out by email as a Microsoft Office form. Both surveys should take approximately 15 minutes to complete. I will also ask your child about their willingness to participate in the interview phase of the study. Choosing to participate in the interviews means that your child will be interviewed for approximately 45 minutes, a week before or during the winter holiday break. The interview will take place over Zoom in a password-protected meeting, outside of class time, and I will find a meeting time that fits your child's schedule. The audio and video data from the interviews will be recorded. Your child will be able to join the Zoom meetings by either downloading the app or

joining from their browser. If they are not comfortable to be on camera, they may choose to turn off their camera.

In total, this study will take less than an hour and a half in total for participation in both interviews as well as the surveys.

C. RISKS AND BENEFITS

There are no anticipated risks of the study. The participants may or may not personally benefit from participating in this research. By taking part in this study, your child might find out which method of learning is most beneficial to them.

D. CONFIDENTIALITY

We will gather the following information as part of this research: Your child's response to both surveys. We will also keep an audio and video recording of the interviews.

We will not allow anyone to access the information, except myself and my supervisor, which does not include the course instructor. We will only use the information for the purposes of the research described in this form. The gathered information will be coded. That means that the information will be identified by a code. I only will have a list that links the code to your child's name.

We will protect the information by keeping it on a password protected hard drive that only I will have access to. This hard drive will always be kept at my house.

We intend to publish the results of the research. However, it will not be possible to identify your child in the published results. We will destroy the information five years after the end of the study.

F. CONDITIONS OF PARTICIPATION

Your child does not have to participate in this research. It is purely you and your child's decision. If your child does participate, your child can withdraw at any time. Participation in this study will not affect your child's course grade in any way. You can also ask that the information your child provided not be used, and your choice will be respected. If your child decides to withdraw from the study, I need to be told within one month of the initial agreement and the data will be removed from the data set immediately after the confirmation of the withdrawal. If your child chooses to withdraw after the one-month period, their data will still be used in the study.

There are no negative consequences for not participating, stopping in the middle, or asking us not to use your child's information.

G. PARENT OR LEGAL GUARDIAN OF THE PARTICIPANT’S DECLARATION

I have read and understood this form. I have had the chance to ask questions and any questions have been answered. I agree to let my child participate in this research under the conditions described.

NAME (please print):

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

NAME OF YOUR CHILD (please print):

If you have questions about the scientific or scholarly aspects of this research, please contact the researcher. Their contact information is on page I. You may also contact their faculty supervisor.

If you have concerns about ethical issues in this research, please contact the Manager, Research Ethics, Concordia University, 514.848.2424 ex. 7481 or oor.ethics@concordia.ca.

Appendix C: Student Consent Form

ASSENT FORM

Study Title: Impact on Student Learning of Online Physics Education

Researcher: Samantha CLARK

Researcher's Contact Information: samanthaclark55@gmail.com

Faculty Supervisor: Dr. Calvin KALMAN

Faculty Supervisor's Contact Information: calvin.kalman@concordia.ca

Source of funding for the study: N/A

My name is Samantha Clark and I graduated from Westwood High School in 2015. I am currently an Honours Physics student at Concordia University completing a thesis under the supervision of Dr. Calvin Kalman. I am inviting you to participate in a research study about the effects of online education on student learning and engagement. Your parent(s) know we are talking with you about the study. This form will tell you about the study to help you decide whether or not you want to take part in it.

What is the key information about this research study?

The following is a short summary of this study to help you decide whether you want to be a part of this study. Information that is more detailed is listed later on in this form.

In this study we are looking at how online learning affects student learning, and participation in a physics course. If you participate, you will be asked to fill out two surveys sent to you as a Microsoft Office form. I will also be asking you to participate in the interview phase of the study if you wish. The interview will take place over Zoom, outside of class time, and I will find a meeting time that suits you. In total, participating in this study will take about 30 minutes if you only complete the surveys, and less than an hour and a half in total if you participate in the interview process and complete both surveys. There are no anticipated risks for taking part in the study. You may or may not personally benefit from participating in this research. Your participation will contribute to a greater understanding of student-centered teaching and online learning strategies.

Why is this study being done?

The purpose of the study is to observe how teaching physics online affects the student's learning and their motivation to learn. You are being asked to take part in the study because you are currently enrolled in a physics course that is offered both online and in person.

What do I need to do?

If you decide to be in the study, both you and your parent or legal guardian will need to sign the forms sent to you. If you also want to do the interviews, you need to send me an email at: samanthaclark55@gmail.com which needs to be signed by both you and your parent or legal guardian.

What are the benefits to me?

If you take part in this study, you might find out which method of learning is most effective for you.

Are there any risks to me if I decide to be involved in this study?

There are no foreseeable risks, however some kids might find that filling out the surveys takes a long time. If you do become tired or bored, it is okay to take breaks and do the surveys in small portions at a time. The same thing goes for the interviews, if you become tired, let me know. We will take a short break. If you have any questions or concerns about any of the questions, please let me know and I will help you.

How will my information be protected?

Your responses will be coded. That means that any gathered information from you will be identified by a code. I will be the only one with a list that links the code to your name. After asking for your permission, the video and audio from the interviews will be recorded. I will not allow anyone to access the information, except the people directly involved in conducting the research. This does not include the teacher. I will only use the information for the research described in this form. All the information will be stored on a password protected hard drive. I will be the only one with access to the hard drive. The results of this study may be used in reports, presentations, or publications but your name will not be used. I will destroy the information five years after the end of the study.

Do I have to be in the study?

No, you don't. The choice is yours. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. No one will get angry or upset if you don't want to do this. And you can change your mind anytime if you decide you don't want to be in the study anymore. Your choice to participate in this study will not affect your grade in any way. If you do choose to leave the study, you need to let me know within the first month of the study. If you leave within the first month, all your data will be deleted. If you leave after the first month, your data will still be used in the study.

What if I have questions?

If you have questions about the study, you can ask me now or anytime during the study. You can e-mail me at: samanthaclark55@gmail.com. You can also email my supervisor at: calvin.kalman@concordia.ca. If you have concerns about ethical issues in this research, please

contact the Manager, Research Ethics, Concordia University, 514.848.2424 ex. 7481 or oor.ethics@concordia.ca. You will receive a copy of this form for your records.

Signing below means that you have read this form and that you are willing to be in this study.

NAME (please print):

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

Appendix D: Instructor Information and Consent Form

INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORM

Study Title: Impact on Student Learning of Online Physics Education

Researcher: Samantha CLARK

Researcher's Contact Information: samanthaclark55@gmail.com

Faculty Supervisor: Dr. Calvin KALMAN

Faculty Supervisor's Contact Information: calvin.kalman@concordia.ca

Source of funding for the study: N/A

You are being invited to participate in the research study mentioned above. This form provides information about what participating would mean. Please read it carefully before deciding if you want to participate or not. If there is anything you do not understand, or if you want more information, please ask me.

A. PURPOSE

The purpose of the research is to investigate the impact of online education on student learning and engagement. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the delivery of educational content had to quickly be adjusted in order to comply with guidelines put in place by authorities to reduce the infection spread. The goal of this project is to observe the impact of these new educational methods on both students and instructors, and to use these observations to propose a pedagogical model that is beneficial to all parties involved.

B. PROCEDURES

If you participate, you will be interviewed during the first part of the academic year. You will be interviewed for approximately 45 minutes. The interview will take place over Zoom in a password-protected meeting, outside of class time, and I will find a meeting time that fits your schedule. The audio and video data from the interviews will be recorded. You will be able to join the Zoom meetings by either downloading the app or joining from your browser. If you are not comfortable to be on camera, you can turn off your camera. In total, participating in this study will less than an hour.

C. RISKS AND BENEFITS

There are no anticipated risks of the study.

You may or may not personally benefit from participating in this research.

D. CONFIDENTIALITY

We will gather the following information as part of this research: the audio and video recording of the interviews. We will not allow anyone to access the information, except myself and my supervisor. We will only use the information for the purposes of the research described in this form. The gathered information will be coded. That means that the information will be identified by a code. I only will have a list that links the code to your name. We will protect the information by keeping it on a password protected hard drive that only the investigators will have access to. This hard drive will always be kept at my house. We intend to publish the results of the research. However, it will not be possible to identify you in the published results. We will destroy the information five years after the end of the study.

F. CONDITIONS OF PARTICIPATION

You do not have to participate in this research. If you do participate, you can withdraw at any time. You can also ask that the information you provided not be used, and your choice will be respected. If you decide to withdraw from the study, I need to be told within one month of the initial agreement and the data will be removed from the data set immediately after the confirmation of your withdrawal. If you choose to withdraw after the one-month period, your data will still be used in the study.

There are no negative consequences for not participating, stopping in the middle, or asking us not to use your information.

G. PARTICIPANT'S DECLARATION

I have read and understood this form. I have had the chance to ask questions and any questions have been answered. I agree to participate in this research under the conditions described.

NAME (please print):

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

If you have questions about the scientific or scholarly aspects of this research, please contact the researcher. Their contact information is on page 1. You may also contact their faculty supervisor.

If you have concerns about ethical issues in this research, please contact the Manager, Research Ethics, Concordia University, 514.848.2424 ex. 7481 or oor.ethics@concordia.ca.

Appendix E: First Survey – October 2020

First Student Survey - 2020 Honours Thesis

* Required

* This form will record your name, please fill your name.

1. (Please selected all that apply) You are taking this course because: *

- You plan on pursuing a career that involves knowing physics.
- Physics knowledge is something that you think is important to have in life.
- Your parents told you to take this course.
- You think learning physics is fun.
- Having physics knowledge will help you be more successful.
- Other

2. (Please select all that apply) You think this course will be: *

- Time-consuming
- Challenging
- Motivating
- Interesting
- Fun

3. (Please select all that apply) Before ONLINE class you: *

- Read about a topic before the teacher has started to teach it.
- Read the posted lecture material.
- Take notes about the material you've read ahead of time.
- Print the posted lecture material but don't look at it.

4. (Please select all that apply) Before IN-PERSON class you: *

- Read about a topic before the teacher has started to teach it.
- Read the posted lecture material.
- Take notes about the material you've read ahead of time.
- Print the posted lecture material but don't look at it.

5. (Please select all that apply) During ONLINE class, you: *

- Hand-write your notes
- Type your notes
- Ask questions out loud
- Ask questions through the chat
- Ask questions by email
- Ask your friends questions (private chat, email, text)

6. (Please select all that apply) During IN-PERSON class, you: *

- Hand-write your notes
- Type your notes
- Raise your hand and ask questions out loud
- Write down your questions to ask the teacher later
- Ask your question to the classmates sitting near you

7. During ONLINE class, you: *

- Always have your camera on
- Only turn on your camera when talking to the teacher
- Have your camera off, except if asked to turn it on
- Don't have a camera, so it's always off

8. (Please select all that apply) AFTER class ONLINE, you: *

- Immediately ask your classmates questions
- Immediately contact the teacher with your questions
- Try to figure out what you don't understand first, and only ask for help if you are really stuck
- Take a break, and look at the class material later

9. (Please select all that apply) AFTER class IN-PERSON, you: *

- Immediately ask your classmates questions
- Immediately contact the teacher with your questions
- Try to figure out what you don't understand first, and only ask for help if you are really stuck
- Take a break, and look at the class material later

10. (Please select all that apply) To learn physics, you need: *

- To read the textbook and/or the notes
- To make summaries
- To make flash cards
- To do many practice questions
- To do some research on your own
- Lectures
- Hands-on activities like labs
- Group projects
- Demonstrations
- Videos
- Explain what you understand to someone
- Have someone explain what they understand to you

11. You prefer learning and working *

- On your own
- In small groups (2-4 people)
- In medium groups (5-8 people)
- In large groups (9-12 people)
- With the whole class

12. Rank the place where you work best on assignments and study. (Top is the best, bottom is where you least prefer to work) *

In a library

During in-class work periods

At home

In public spaces like the cafeteria, park, coffee shop, etc.

13. You prefer to attend class lectures *

- In person
- Online

14. (Please select all that apply) When the course is online you think: *

- It is easier to participate in class discussions
- It is easier to ask questions
- You can get more help
- Classes are more enjoyable
- It is easier to do assignments
- It is easier to do tests
- You can focus on the material better
- You are safer

15. (Please select all that apply) Who would you be able to ask for help if you had any questions about the physics material? *

- Friends
- Classmates
- Parent(s) or legal guardian(s)
- The teacher
- Tutor

16. Name at least three advantages of doing class online: *

17. Name at least three challenges of doing class online: *

18. Name at least three advantages of doing class in-person: *

19. Name at least three challenges of doing class in-person: *

Demographics

This section will only be used to better organize the data. Your answers to the following questions will not be part of the final paper except in the context of describing the data. For example, "there was a positive correlation between students who identified as auditory learners and their preference to attend class online." The preferred pronouns section will also be used as a way to avoid misgendering during the research process. If you have any concerns with any of these questions please send me an email and we'll figure it out together.

20. Please specify your preferred pronouns: *

- She/Her
- He/Him
- They/Them
- Other

21. Based on the grades you've received for this course so far and in other science classes, how would you describe yourself in terms of academic performance? *

- Above average (85% or more overall)
- Average (between 84% and 70% overall)
- Below average (Below 70% overall)

22. Of the following types of learners, which do you think best describes you? *

- You learn best by looking at images, charts or concept maps. You like to make outlines or lists to study.
- You learn best by reading the material out loud or explaining what you understand to someone.
- You learn best by physically interacting with the material and doing.

23. Do you want to be part of the interview process? *

Yes

No

24. What is your email address? *

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

 Microsoft Forms

Appendix F: Second Survey – December 2020

Second Student Survey - 2020 Honours Thesis

* Required

* This form will record your name, please fill your name.

1. Please check all statements that you AGREE with: *

- You are happy with the amount of knowledge you have gained from this course so far.
- Your understanding of physics has changed since taking the course.
- You can see yourself applying knowledge gained from this course in your day to day life.
- You are glad you are taking this course.
- You would recommend this course to a friend.

2. (Please select all that apply) So far, you think this course has been: *

- Time-consuming
- Challenging
- Motivating
- Interesting
- Fun
- Useful

3. Please check all statements that you AGREE with: *

- You were able to work on things that interested you in this course.
- The teacher took the students' perspectives into account and explained why she had you perform certain activities or made certain decisions.
- You always understood what you were expected to do.

4. Please check all statements that you AGREE with: *

- You spent about the same time on this course compared to your other courses.
- You think it was an appropriate amount of time to spend on this course.
- The teacher gave you enough time to complete assignments.

5. Please check all statements that you AGREE with: *

- Your grades reflect your expectations.
- You are satisfied in the way you were graded for assignments.
- You are satisfied with the grading structure.
- You are satisfied with the amount of work that is being used to assign your grade.

6. Please check all statements that you AGREE with: *

- You think you get the same quality of education by taking a course online rather than in person.
- So far, you think your experience with online learning has been similar to your classmates' experiences.
- Compared to the start of the school year, your opinion about taking a course online has changed.

7. List three new advantages that you have discovered by doing the course ONLINE: *

8. List three new disadvantages that you have encountered by doing the course ONLINE: *

9. What would you have changed in the way the class was taught so far? Please mention at least 2 different things. *

10. Explain how your learning experience is different when it's online versus in-person. *

11. Describe how the type of learner you are affects your ONLINE learning experience AND explain how it could be different for a different learner. *

12. Describe how the type of learner you are affects your IN-PERSON learning experience AND explain how it could be different for a different learner. *

13. Rank the method that makes you understand the material the most during class time. (Top is the best, bottom is the worst) *

Listening to the teacher in person

Listening to the teacher online

Doing the labs

Having someone other than the teacher explain what they understand to you

Watching videos

Reading the notes and/or the textbook

Watching a live demonstration

Seeing the teacher solve example problems

Working on a group project

14. Rank the method that makes you understand the material the most when you are studying (outside of class). (Top is the best, bottom is the least helpful/something you don't do) *

Re-reading the notes

Making summaries

Making flash cards

Solving as many practice questions as you can

Doing some research on your own

Watching videos

Explaining what you understand to someone else

Having someone explaining what they understand to you

Working with a tutor

15. What has been the most stressful part of this school year for you so far? *

16. Based on the grades you've received so far for this course, how would you describe yourself in terms of academic performance? *

- Above average (85% or more)
- Average (Between 84% and 70%)
- Below Average (Below 70%)

17. What is your email address? *

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

 Microsoft Forms

Appendix G: Student Interview Guide

- What are the factors that made you decide to take this course? Is there another course that you would have wanted to take instead? If so why, or why not?
- How much do you think learning physics will be useful to you in your life? Why? Is there anything you have learned so far that you think won't be useful? Why?
- How would you describe the experience to a friend who is not in this class?
 - ex. The way this class is taught?
- Had you ever taken courses similar to this one in terms of teaching methods before?
 - What teaching methods are you used to?
 - What was new?
- Do you think your initial expectations for the course are reflected in how the course has gone so far?
- What would you tell your past-self right before starting this course?
- Did your study method change over time?
- How do you keep yourself on track?
- Before starting the class, did you have any specific concerns about taking this course? Were those concerns valid? Did new concerning situations come up?
- How is your motivation level to attend classes online compared to in-person? Did your motivation change over time? Why?
- How did you think your learning experience will change by taking the course online rather than in person? Have you noticed those changes?
- What would you change about the way this course was taught to you? If you were a teacher how would you teach this course differently?
- Why would you recommend this course to a friend? Why not?

- What advice would you have for new students taking this course?
- Has your opinion about taking a course online changed?
- Do you think all classes should be switched to online learning? Why?
- Do you think you get the same quality of education by taking a course online rather than in person?
- Rank the type of classes (in-person, half/half, online) and why?
- Do you think your experience with online learning was similar your classmates' experiences?
If so, in what ways?
- What have we not talked about that we should have?

Appendix H: Teacher Interview Guide

- What changes have you made to your teaching method in the switch to online education?
- Is there any content that you've added or omitted due to the switch? If so, why or why not?
- What are your biggest worries with teaching a course online rather than in-person?
- What do you think the benefits are to teach the course online?
- How has your course preparation changed?
- In what ways do you think the switch to online education will affect the students? Why?
- How has the evaluation (tests, exams, etc.) component of your course changed?

- How has the participation component of your course changed?
- How has the assignment delivery and grading of your course changed?
- Describe how you think the transition between in-person education to online education has gone so far.
 - What do you think could have made it better?
 - What were the obstacles you've had to overcome so far?
 - What was useful in making this transition go the way it did?